

SPATIAL AND TIME ANTARCTIC OZONE CHANGES IN CONNECTION WITH SUDDEN STRATOSPHERIC WARMINGS

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Major sudden stratospheric warmings (SSW) are typical for the northern high-latitude winter stratosphere but rare over Antarctica. Only the 2002 event was identified as a major SSW with a reversal of westerly zonal wind to easterly at the altitudinal level of 10 hPa. In addition, the warming events of 1988 and 2019 were comparable in terms of many characteristics (including changes in zonal wind velocity). These events resulted in significant variations of various atmospheric parameters, particularly the total ozone column (TOC). The variations can be different depending on the coordinates of an observational point. To solve this problem, we have used Multi-Sensor Reanalysis data (<https://temis.nl/>). In this work, we have analyzed TOC variations in the range of 2 months before and after a sudden stratospheric warming. Total ozone climatology based on the data for more than 4 decades (from 1979 hitherto) is determined to compare the years with the warmings with other ones. We have noticed a different spatial pattern with the higher TOC values in East Antarctica. Similar and distinct features of each of the phenomena are evaluated.

We have also determined minor stratospheric warmings from Antarctica's temperature and zonal wind distributions (<https://ozonewatch.gsfc.nasa.gov/meteorology/SH.html>). More than 20 phenomena of this type are identified, giving a basis for a statistical analysis. The influence of these events on the TOC variations is also determined, although it is less significant compared to the SSW events of 1988, 2002, and 2019.

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